

PYRONES AND RELATED COMPOUNDS. PART II. A NEW REACTION PRODUCT OF ACETONE DICARBOXYLIC ACID AND ACETIC ANHYDRIDE

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By the action of four molecules of acetic anhydride on one molecule of acetone dicarboxylic acid a new acid, $C_8H_8O_8$, is obtained, to which a tentative structure is assigned.

The action of acetic anhydride on acetone dicarboxylic acid is known to give the following products :

(i) Dehydracetocarboxylic acid (I) (Pechmann and Neger, *Annalen*, 1893, 273, 186).

(ii) Acetone dicarboxylic anhydride (II) and the mixed anhydride (III) of acetone dicarboxylic acid and acetic acid (Willstätter, *Annalen*, 1922, 42B, 422).

(iii) Dihydroxypyronone (IV), isolated by one of us (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*; 1940, 17 138).

In one of the somewhat large scale preparation of dihydroxypyronone (IV) a new acid, m.p. 154° , has been obtained.

From the melting point it was thought to be identical with dehydracetocarboxylic acid (I, m.p. 154°), but a comparison between the two revealed some differences in their physical and chemical properties. Both are acids. The compound (I) dissolves in aqueous potash and on adding excess of acetic acid to the alkaline solution, the mono-potassium salt of the acid separates (Pechmann and Neger, *loc. cit.*). The new acid, however, behaves differently.

The new acid, $C_9H_8O_5$, seems to have been formed from one molecule of acetone dicarboxylic acid and one molecule of acetic anhydride by elimination of three molecules of water.

The structure of the acid seems to be (V) formed in the following manner (*cf.* Phillippi and Seka, *Ber.*, 1921, 54B, 1089).

This is confirmed by the fact that dehydracetocarboxylic acid (I) on crystallisation from acetic anhydride gives a solid whose melting and the mixed melting point with the acid (V) was found to be 157° . But the reverse change from (V) to (I) could not be realised so far.

EXPERIMENTAL

100 G. pure acetone dicarboxylic acid were treated with 200 g. of acetic anhydride. As usual the pyrone separated after standing overnight and was removed by filtration. The mother-liquor was allowed to evaporate at room temperature. From the resulting solid a second crop of the pyrone was obtained and another substance which after purification melted at 154° . It dissolves in aqueous potash and from the solution on standing its potassium derivative separates without addition of acetic acid. The potassium derivative was filtered at the pump, washed with a little dilute alcohol and dissolved in water. A part of the aqueous solution of the potassium derivative was acidified with hydrochloric acid when the new acid precipitated. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol, from which it separated as prisms melting at 157° . [Found : C, 54.8 ; H, 3.2 ; Equiv. by titration, 192 ; as silver salt, 188. $C_9H_8O_5$ requires C, 55.6 ; H, 3.1 per cent. Equiv., 194. $C_9H_8O_6$ (I) requires C, 50.9 ; H, 3.7 per cent].

Its aniline salt was prepared by dissolving equimolecular quantities of the acid and the aniline separately in ether and mixing the two solutions. The aniline salt precipitated at once. It was filtered, washed with ether and crystallised from alcohol

as long yellow needles, m.p. 185°. (Found : C, 62.9 ; H, 4.4 ; N, 5.2. $C_{15}H_{13}O_3N$ requires C, 62.9 ; H, 4.8 ; N, 4.9 per cent).

When acetone dicarboxylic acid (one molecule) was treated with four molecules of acetic anhydride in the manner in which the dihydroxypyrrone is prepared (*loc. cit.*), the sole product of the reaction is the acid (V), m.p. 157°.

In the formation of the dihydroxypyrrone one molecule of water is eliminated from one molecule of acetonedicarboxylic acid, as such the preparation of the dihydroxypyrrone was modified since the publication of the paper (*loc. cit.*).

On addition of acetonedicarboxylic acid (one molecule) to two molecules of acetic anhydride instead of two and half molecules, the acid went into solution as usual with the evolution of heat. After allowing it to remain for 4 hours and seeding the dihydroxypyrrone separated as small shining plates. This was left overnight and the next day it was filtered, washed and dried ; yield however improved a little. In this manner 20 g. of acetone dicarboxylic acid gave 12.5 g. of dihydroxypyrrone.

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MOLAR REFRACTION AND THE STRUCTURE OF OXYMETHYLENE KETONES

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The values of the molar refraction of ethoxymethylene acetone and ethoxymethylene methylethyl ketone are recorded and the results confirm the structure assigned to oxymethylene acetone and oxymethylene methylethyl ketone on other grounds.

On physicochemical evidence oxymethylene acetone and oxymethylene methylethyl ketone are shown to possess the structure (I) and (II) (R = H) (*cf.* Kaushal, Sovani and Deshapande, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 108 ; Joshi, Kaushal and Deshapande, *ibid.*, 1941, 18, 479).

The molecule of (I) or (II) possesses a conjugated double bond, and their molar refraction has been studied. Oxymethylene acetone is unstable and oxymethylene methylethyl ketone is a solid, m.p. 72° (*loc. cit.*). Hence to study the molar refractions their ethyl ethers have been prepared by condensing the crude sodio derivatives of (I) or (II) with ethyl halide in alcoholic suspension.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethoxymethylene acetone (I, R = C_2H_5) was prepared by treating the sodium oxymethylene acetone (from 12 g. acetone, 20 g. formic ester and 5 g. sodium wire in dry ether) with 37 g. of ethyl bromide in 250 c. c. of absolute alcohol and allowing